

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ATORVASTATIN,
EZETIMIBEIN AND FENOFIBRATE BULK AND
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS BY RP-HPLC****M.Arjun¹, M.Chaitanya², P.Aravindra Reddy³**

Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy, N.F.C Nagar, Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.

Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

RP-HPLC method was developed and validated as per ICH guidelines for the estimation of. Atorvastatin, Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate Simultaneous Estimation of Atorvastatin, and Ezetimibe were carried out by RP- HPLC using potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer & acetonitrile, and C₁₈ G analytical column as a stationary phase and peak was observed at 265 nm which was selected as a wavelength for quantitative estimation. After the development of the method, it was validated for various parameters. It was found that recovery value of pure drug was between 99 % to 101% which indicates that the method is accurate and also reveals that commonly used excipients and additives present in the pharmaceutical formulations were not interfering in the proposed methods. The ruggedness of the method was checked by different analysts and found that the results were nearly same which indicates that the method is rugged. Based on the results observed, it was concluded that proposed method can be used for routine analysis of Atorvastatin , Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate

Key words: *Atorvastatin and Ezetimibe, Fenofibrate ,linearity, accuracy, precision.***Corresponding author:****M.Chaitanya,**Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy,
N.F.C Nagar, Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.

QR code

Please cite this article in press **M.Chaitanya et al Method Development And Validation For Simultaneous Estimation Of Atorvastatin, Ezetimibein And Fenofibrate Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms By Rp-Hplc., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).**

INTRODUCTION:

HPLC today is the product of quarter century of refinement, driven by technical advances and economic competition in a USD 2 Billion plus equipment market. Recently, manufactures have improved HPLC'S performance easier.

Atorvastatin calcium, is [R-(R*,R*)]-2-(4-fluorophenyl)-β,δ-dihydroxy-5-(1-methyl ethyl)-3-phenyl-4-[(phenylamino)carbonyl]-1Hpyrrole-1-heptanoic acid, calcium salt (2:1) trihydrate. The empirical formula of atorvastatin calcium is (C₃₃H₃₄FN₂O₅)₂Ca•3H₂O and its molecular weight is 1209.42. Atorvastatin is an inhibitor of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutarylcoenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase. This enzyme catalyzes the conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate, an early and rate-limiting step in cholesterol biosynthesis [1-2]. The typical dose of Atorvastatin calcium is 10-80 mg per day and it reduces 40-60% LDL[4].

Ezetimibe, (1-(4-fluorophenyl)-3(R)-[3(S)-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-hydroxy propyl]-4(S)-(4-hydroxyphenyl) azetidino-2-one), which belongs to a group of selective and very effective 2-azetidione cholesterol absorption inhibitors acts at the level of cholesterol entry into enterocytes [4]. It prevents transport of cholesterol through the intestinal wall by selectively blocking the absorption of cholesterol from dietary and biliary sources. This reduces the overall delivery of cholesterol to the liver, thereby promoting the synthesis of LDL receptors and a subsequent reduction in serum LDL-C [5-6].

Fenofibrate is an anti-lipemic agent which reduces both cholesterol and triglycerides in the blood. Fenofibrate exerts its therapeutic effects through activation of peroxisome proliferator activated receptor α (PPARα). This increases lipolysis and elimination of triglyceride-rich particles from plasma by activating lipoprotein lipase and reducing production of aipoprotein C-III. The resulting fall in triglycerides produces an alteration in the size and composition of LDL from small, dense particles, to large buoyant particles. These larger particles have a greater affinity for cholesterol receptors and are catabolized rapidly. Fenofibrate is chemically known as propan-2-yl 2-{4-[(4-chlorophenyl) carbonyl] phenoxy}-2-methylpropanoate. The Molecular Formula is C₂₀H₂₁ClO₄ and Molecular weight is 360.83.

The main objective of the present work is to establish a stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous

determination of Atorvastatin, Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate in combined dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

HPLC with WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 separation module, PDA detector. All chemicals were AR grade.

HPLC method development and validation:**Mobile phase optimization:**

Initially the mobile phase tried was methanol: Ammonium acetate buffer and Methanol: phosphate buffer with various combinations of pH as well as varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to potassium dihydrogen phosphate with buffer (pH 3.0), Methanol in proportion 30: 70 v/v respectively.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of Atorvastatin Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate in diluents (mobile phase composition) was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum wavelength selected as 265nm. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of column:

The method was performed with various columns like C₁₈ column, hypersil column, lichrosorb, and inertsil ODS column. Inertsil ODS (4.6 x 150mm, 5μm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 0.8ml/min flow.

Preparation of phosphate buffer:

After dissolving 100 grammes of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate in 800 millilitres of HPLC-grade water and using hydrochloric acid to bring the pH down to 3.3, 1000 millilitres of HPLC-grade water were used.

Preparation of mobile phase:

A solution of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.3) and acetonitrile (10:90 v/v) was made, were mixed and degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of the Atorvastatin Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate & sample solution:

EZ, FE, and AT calcium stock solutions were made in acetonitrile. To obtain the final concentrations of 10, 20, 40, 80, and 100 μg/mL for AT and EZ; and 160, 320, 640, 1280, and

1600 µg/mL for FE, aliquots of standard stock solutions of AT, EZ, and FE were transferred to bulb pipettes into a 100 mL volumetric flask. The solution was then made up to volume with acetonitrile.

Chromatographic separation:

It was performed using an enable C18 G analytical column and a mobile phase consisting of phosphate buffer and acetonitrile injected at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. A light diode array detector tuned at 265 nm was used to detect the column effluents. The injection volume of the sample was 20 µL.

System suitability:

Tailing factor for the peaks due to Atorvastatin Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate in standard solution should not be more than 2.0. Theoretical plates for the Atorvastatin Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate peaks in standard solution should not be less than 2000.

Accuracy:

A known drug concentration spiked with formulation in triplicate was analysed to determine accuracy, and the recovery percentage was then calculated.

determine accuracy, and the recovery percentage was then calculated.

Robustness:

The purpose of the robustness study was to evaluate the impact of small changes in the ideal chromatographic parameters. Intentional changes were made to the separation parameters, such as the flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min) and the percentage of acetonitrile in the mobile phase ($\pm 2\%$). The suggested approach and the resulting responses to the modifications were statistically compared.

Assay of Commercial Formulation:

Twenty tablets of three drugs from the same batch were weighed and ground into a fine powder in order to prepare the sample. A 100 mL volumetric flask was then filled with tablet powder equal to 5 mg of AT, 5 mg of EZ, and 80 mg of FE, which was then dissolved in acetonitrile. To obtain the stock solution, the volume was adjusted using the same solvent after the instant dissolution and filtered through a 0.45 µm filter. To obtain the working standard solution, 5 mL of the stock solution was further diluted to 50 mL and filtered. Then, in ideal chromatographic conditions, the filtrate was loaded onto the HPLC.

Optimized chromatographic conditions

Parameters	Conditions
Stationary phase	An enable C18 G
Mobile Phase	Phosphate buffer and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 10:90 v/v.
Column temperature (°C)	Ambient
Wavelength (nm)	265
Flow rate (mL/min)	1 mL
Injection Volume	20 µL
Run time	10 min
AT RT (min)	3.155 \pm 0.5 min
EZ RT (min)	5.299 \pm 0.5 min
FE RT (min)	6.215 \pm 0.5 min

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Fig. 3: Chromatogram of standard AT, EZ and FE at optimum condition

Under the optimum chromatographic conditions, the retention time obtained for AT, EZ and FE was 3.155, 5.299 and 6.215 minutes respectively. The system suitability parameters (retention time, tailing factor, Number of theoretical plates and resolution) obtained are found to be within the acceptance criteria indicating the fitness of the method for separation and determination of the compounds.

Validation of the method:

The following parameters were used to validate the analytical method:

LOQ and LOD:

When compared to the published approaches, the acquired data show that the method is extremely sensitive.

Precision:

The study's superimposed chromatograms are shown in Fig. 2.6. For intra- and inter-day precision studies, the findings from the precision investigation of AT, EZ, and FE are shown in Table 2.6. The method's suitability for precision was demonstrated by the computed percentage RSD values for the intra-day precision study being less than 0.27% and the inter-day study being less than 0.201%.

Table 7: Precision study of AT, EZ and FE

Drug	Intra-day	Inter-day
	Peak area	Peak area
AT	201945.55 ± 47.36; 0.018	201885.6 ± 43.35; 0.018
EZ	199102.6 ± 544.18; 0.32	199248 ± 406.52; 0.2198
FE	3224705.5 ± 2658.54; 0.08	3225004.1 ± 2017.4; 0.08

Assay of formulation:

For each of the three analytes, the medication concentrations in the tablet dosage forms were determined to be greater than 99.21%.

The data obtained was presented in **Table 9** and the represented formulation chromatogram was shown in **Fig. 2.7**.

Table 9: Assay of formulation

Fibator tablets	AT	EZ	FE
Labelled amount in mg	10	10	160
% Assay	99.67	99.21	99.57

Fig:Chromatogram of commercial formulation

System suitability study:

System appropriateness is utilised to guarantee that the chromatographic system performs adequately and is a crucial component of method development. Table 2.10 displays the parameters for the system suitability test (SST). The system's suitability was confirmed by

the SST findings, which show that it conforms with peak parameter constraints. The method's strong selectivity is confirmed by the resolution (> 3.32), peak asymmetry (< 2.0), and overall analysis duration of 6.220 minutes.

Table 11: System suitability parameters for AT, EZ and FE

Parameter	Values obtained			Preferable Values
	AT	EZ	FE	
Retention time	3.160	5.230	6.220	10 min
Theoretical plates	30627.96	38458.597	41035.9	> 2500
Resolution	-	8.990	3.325	> 1.5
Tailing factor	1.570	1.595	1.690	< 2.0

CONCLUSION:

For the simultaneous measurement of three drugs in bulk and tablet formulation, a straightforward and effective reversed-phase HPLC method was created, and it was verified in compliance with ICH guidelines. During validation, the approach was determined to be robust, sensitive, linear, accurate, and exact. The validation of the method yielded

satisfactory results. The technique is suitable for regular analysis.

REFERENCES:

- Collins R, Armitage J, Parish S. MRC/BHF Heart Protection Study of cholesterol lowering with simvastatin in 20,536 high-risk individuals:

- a randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2002; 360:7-22.
- Genest J, Pherson RMc, Frolich J, Anderson T, Campbell N, Carpentier A, et al. Canadian Cardiovascular Society/Canadian guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of dyslipidemia and prevention of cardiovascular disease in the adult recommendations. *Canadian Journal of Cardiology*. 2009; 25(10):567- 579.
 - Knopp RH, Gitter H, Truitt T, Bays H, Manion CV, Lipka LJ, et al. Ezetimibe Study Group. Effects of ezetimibe, a new cholesterol absorption inhibitor, on plasma lipids in patients with primary hypercholesterolemia. *European Heart Journal*. 2003; 24:729-741.
 - Kosoglou T, Statkevich P, Fruchart JC. Pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic interaction between fenofibrate and ezetimibe. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 2004; 20:1197-1207.
 - Ramjattan BR, Callaghan DJG, Theiss U. Efficacy and tolerability of a "suprabioavailable" formulation of fenofibrate in patients with dyslipidemia: A pooled analysis of two open-label trials. *Clinical Therapeutics Journal*. 2002; 24:1105-1116.
 - Sujana SK, Lahey KA, Day A, LaHaye SA. Comparison of the efficacy of administering a combination of ezetimibe plus fenofibrate versus atorvastatin monotherapy in the treatment of dyslipidemia. *Lipids Health Disease Journal*. 2009; 8:56.doi:10.1186/1476-511X-8-56.
 - Lemke TL, Williams DA, Roche VF, Zito WS (Ed). *Foye's Principles of Medicinal Chemistry*, 7th edition, Chapter 25, antihyperlipoproteinemics and inhibitors of cholesterol biosynthesis, Wolters Kluwer; Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2013; pp. 827-837.
 - CIMS (Current Index of Medical Specialities), UBM Medica India Pvt. Limited, Bangalore, pp. 140-142, Jan. - Apr. (2016).
 - Patel A, Macwana C, Parmar V, Patel S. Simultaneous determination of atorvastatin calcium, ezetimibe, and fenofibrate in a tablet formulation by HPLC. *Journal of AOAC International*. 2012; 95(2):419-423.
 - Choudhari VP and Nikalje AP. Simultaneous Estimation of Atorvastatin, Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate in Pharmaceutical Formulation by RP-LC-PDA. *Pharmaceutica Analytica Acta Journal*. 2010; 1:111.doi:10.4172/2153-2435.1000111.
 - Abhijit DD, Padmanabh DB, Santosh GV, Sujith N, Suvarna V. A Simple and Sensitive RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Atorvastatin Calcium, Ezetimibe and Fenofibrate in Combined Tablet Dosage Form. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2013; 6(10):1085-1088.